

SELF- Esteem and its Relationship with Burnout Phenomenon among Teachers of Physical Education in the Middle School Stage

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Abstract

The study strived to illuminate the nature of the correlation between self-esteem and burnout, as well as the level of each among middle school teachers of physical education and sports in BatnaCity, and also explored the influence of marital status on those teachers. The study employed a descriptive approach, randomly opted for a sample size of 143 teachers from the total target population of 312, and relied on the Maslach burnout scale and the Rosenberg self-esteem scale to gather data. The findings suggest that the participants exhibited an exceptional level of self-esteem and a low level of psychological burnout. A noteworthy and adverse correlation exists between the two variables, while no statistically significant disparities are observed between the same two variables contingent upon marital status.

Keywords: Self-Esteem, Burnout, Teachers of Physical Education, Middle School Stage.

1. INTRODUCTION

The vocation of teaching is commonly perceived as a highly esteemed profession, characterized by significant demands and expectations placed upon the teacher. According to Wardah (2016), the teaching profession has been categorized by the International Labor Organization (ILO) as one of the most demanding occupations.

Based on a study conducted by Nejad in 2013, teachers of physical education and sports are more likely to experience job-related stress compared to their peers. This heightened stress may lead to burnout, ultimately impacting the teacher's self-esteem in a negative manner.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

The jeopardy of burnout among physical education and sports teachers is that it is associated with job inefficacy and therefore profoundly affects the advancement of the class, as evidenced by several studies, including those conducted by Ghidi Abdel Qader (2012) and Salem Lakhdar (2019, p. 496).

According to DardirNashwaKaram (2007), "it is necessary for physical education and sports teachers to have a strong personality in order to effectively confront this phenomenon." Karam stated that burnout can occur due to factors related to the work environment as well as individual personality traits". In this context, the researcher conducted an investigation that looked into the relationship between self-esteem, burnout, and marital status among physical education and sports teachers.

The study aimed to shed light on the impact of work-related stress on teachers' personal lives as well as the potential for personal issues to affect their work performance. Consequently, the researcher attempted to address the following inquiry: Can a statistically significant correlation be observed between the dimensions of burnout and self-esteem among middle school teachers?

1.2. The hypothesis of the Study

The study hypotheses can be formulated as follows:

The general hypothesis:

There is a statistically significant relationship between burnout and self-esteem among middle school teachers of physical education and sports.

Secondary hypotheses:

- A- The effect of psychological burnout on teachers of physical education and sports in the preparatory stage is at a medium level.
- B- With regard to the variable of marital status, there are statistically significant disparities in the burnout phenomenon among middle school teachers of physical education and sports.
- C- The teachers of physical education and sports in the preparatory grade have an average level of self-esteem.
- D- There exist statistically significant disparities in the burnout phenomenon among middle school teachers of physical education and sports attributed to the marital status variable.

1.3. Significance of the Study

The value of the study stems from the fact that it investigates a topic that, to the extent of the researcher's knowledge, has not been the focus of previous studies on this category of society. It also highlights the serious repercussions that burnout and low self-esteem may have on the health and performance of teachers.

1.4. The Aim of the Study

The purpose of this study is to determine the level of burnout and self-esteem among the sample participants, and disclose the nature of this relationship, as well as to emphasize the differences with regard to the variable of marital status.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

- A- Friedman and Farb conducted a study with the intention of identifying the school-related factors that are linked to burnout among teachers. The study involved a comparison of the organizational aspects of schools that exhibit high levels of burnout among teachers with those that exhibit low levels of burnout. A research investigation was carried out on a sample of 1597 primary school teachers using the Meslash scale. The findings revealed the existence of multiple factors, among which were a lack of trust in the teachers' professional competence and a negative relationship between self-concept and burnout.
- B- A study by Muhannad AbdSalim (2003) entitled Self-concept and the Influence of Certain Demographic Factors and its relationship to the phenomenon of burnout among public secondary school teachers in the governorates of both Jenin and Nablus. It comprised a total of 280 teachers, both male and female. The Maslash burnout scale and the Tennessee scale for self-concept were utilized to obtain the results. The findings indicated an average level of self-concept, a high level of emotional exhaustion, a low level of lack of sense of achievement, and a medium level of the depersonalization

dimension, as well as a substantial positive relationship between self-concept and burnout across all three dimensions and statistically significant differences for the self-concept in favor of the unmarried teachers.

- C- Abdulaziz Amal Anwa conducted a study on the correlation between burnout, self-control, self-esteem, and various demographic variables among a group of teachers from different educational stages. The sample size for this study was 336 teachers. The findings indicate an existing relation, both positive and negative, between self-esteem and burnout. In addition, the study observed statistically significant differences of the burnout phenomenon among individuals attributed to the marital status in favour of the unmarried individuals.
- D- Qamiha Alaa Mahmoud's study on "Psychological Burnout among Middle School Teachers and its Relationship to Self-Esteem and Some Demographic Variables"(2012). The study sought to uncover this relationship through the design of two scales using a sample of 241 male and female teachers; the results revealed an average level of burnout. There are no statistically significant distinctions attributed to the marital status variable, and a negative correlation exists between exhaustion and self-esteem. However, there is an inverse correlation between burnout and self-esteem.

In Harbash Ibrahim's and other co-researchers study, titled "The Relationship of Occupational Pressures with Self-Esteem among Physical Education and Sports Teachers in Preparatory Grade," the study used a sample of 50 teachers of physical education and sports, half males and half females, and employed the Muhammad Hassan Allawi scale of occupational stress and the Rosenberg scale of self-esteem.

The funding uncovered an inverse correlation between the two; it also showed high self-esteem for both sexes and a low level of burnout for both of them.

3. Operational Definitions

Psychological Burnout: Maslach (1981) defined psychological burnout as “a state of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment that can occur among individuals who work with people in some capacity”.

It includes three distinct elements: Emotional exhaustion, Depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. However, it is known procedurally as the state of psychological and physical disintegration that renders a teacher indifferent to the completion of his work and stubborn in his interactions, as indicated by his total score on the scale used in the study.

Self-esteem: Rosenberg (1979, p. 833) defined it as "a favorable or unfavorable attitude toward the self. "Individuals with high self-esteem generally have a positive self-image, feel confident in their abilities, and have a sense of self-worth, while those with low self-esteem may struggle with feelings of inadequacy, self-doubt, and a negative self-perception.

It is being defined procedurally as an individual's subjective assessment of their own worth, which can be either positive or negative, and is based on their own perceptions and interpretations, and it is shown through his total score on the Rosenberg scale used in this study.

4. THE RESEARCH METHODS

4.1. Survey

A fieldwork visit was conducted to several middle schools with the aim of assessing the appropriateness of the scales for the study sample, identifying potential challenges that may arise in the field, and validating the psychometric properties of the two scales. It was presented to a group of 34 male and female teachers, and they didn't find any problems with it. Subsequently, the questionnaires were redistributed after a time lapse of three to five weeks. Subsequently, the questionnaires were redistributed and collected after a period of three to five weeks. A total of 15 questionnaires were obtained and utilized to measure validity through the reapplication technique.

4.2. Time Horizon

The distribution of questionnaires to participants in Batna city took place between the dates of 02/06/2018 and 02/20/2018.

4.3. Choice of Method

The study employed a descriptive exploratory approach, utilizing both correlation and comparison methods in its research methodology.

4.4. Population and Sample Size

According to statistics obtained from the Directorate of Education in Batna's city, there are 312 middle school teachers of physical education and sports, 292 of whom are men and 20 are women. From this target population, 143 teachers were randomly selected to fill out questionnaires; this proportion accounts for 45.83% of the study population. In addition, 71 of them are married, and 72 of them are unmarried.

4.5. Data Collection Tools

The following two measures were used:

A- Maslack burnout scale:

It consists of 22 items included in 3 essential dimensions: (Emotional exhaustion, Depersonalization, Reduced personal accomplishment). The researcher employed item reversal technique for the "Reduced personal accomplishment" dimension by converting negatively worded items to positively ones.

▪ The psychometric properties of the scale used in this study:

The researcher calculated the reliability of the scale and found out that the calculated (t) values ranged between the values of the upper and lower groups of the dimensions of the scale, and its total score ranged between (3.86 - 9.43), which is greater than the observed (t) value (2.92) at a significance level of (0.01). which shows a high degree of distinction. The validity was verified using Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the items of each dimension with the total score of the scale, and the values of the validity coefficients were (0.82, 0.89, 0.74, 0.71).

B-Morris Rosenberg's self-esteem scale (1965, Rosenberg):

The scale consists of 10 items that measure the general self-esteem of adults, and the researcher has established a standard consisting of three self-esteem levels, as shown in the table below.

Table 01: Levels of self-esteem

Levels of self-esteem			
Level	Low	Average	High
Total Score	1 – 13.33	13.34 – 26.66	26.67 - 40
Test Value	Total degrees of alternatives ÷ number of alternatives x number of paragraphs. = 25		

▪ **The validity and reliability of the scale in the current study:**

The researcher calculated the reliability of the scale, and find out the calculated (t) values ranged between the values of the upper and lower groups of the total score of the scale (7.61), which is greater than the observed (t) value (2.92) at a significance level of (0.01).

Which shows a high degree of distinction. The validity was verified using Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the ten items, as it reached (0.706), at the significance level of 0.05, which means a high level of validity estimated at (0.84).

4.6. Data Procedures Tools

The statistical techniques used through the SPSS-VERSION.24 program are as follows:

- Percentage, mean, and standard deviation.
- Parson's correlation coefficient.
- Alpha de Cronbach coefficient.
- T-test for one sample
- Mann-Whitney U test to verify differences between two groups.
- The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used to test for normal distribution

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Data normal distribution test

By using Kolmogorov-Smirnov, the findings revealed that the p-value ≥ 0.05 related to the participants' responses on the burnout scale. This means that the data conforms to a normal distribution, and parametric tests can be used for analysis.

However, the p-value is ≤ 0.05 on the self-esteem scale for the married teachers' responses. This indicates that the data is not typical of a normal distribution, and therefore non-parametric tests are more appropriate in this case.

5.2. Discussion of the general hypothesis's results

This hypothesis claimed a statistically significant relationship between burnout and self-esteem among teachers of physical education and in Preparatory stage. As shown in the following table, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated across the respondents on the emotional intelligence and burnout scales and their dimensions in order to check the hypothesis.

Table 02: The Pearson correlation coefficient results between the self-esteem scale and burnout and its dimensions

Test value (0.05)			
df (142)			
Dimensions	Total score for self-esteem	R	R ²
Emotional exhaustion	-0.222	0.176	0.0973
Depersonalization	-0.196		
Reduced personal accomplishment	-0.319		
Total score of Burnout	-0.312		

- Table 02 reveals the following:

There is a negative and statistically significant correlation between self-esteem and burnout and its three dimensions. It was estimated at ($r = -0.222$) with the emotional stress dimension, and ($r = -0.319$) with the lack of sense of achievement dimension and ($r = 0.312$) with the total score of burnout, at the level of significance (0.01), estimated at ($r = -0.196$), with the depersonalization dimension at the level (0.05).

These findings validated the hypothesis, namely that a high degree of psychological burnout is associated with a low level of self-esteem, and vice versa. According to Naji Youssef (1999), Rashman (1983, Rashman), psychological burnout is an "emotional stress that leads to negative responses and attitudes toward self and others." "Teachers' sense of burnout affects and is influenced by self-concept," Ali Al-Harmleh (2015, pg. 49).

It is worth mentioning that numerous studies have concurred with the finding that enhancing self-esteem of physical education and sports teachers is imperative in preventing burnout. Particular studies in this regard include those conducted by Friedman and Farber (1991), Ahmed Ali Al-Harmleh (2007), Abdulaziz Anwar (2009), QamihaAlaa Mahmoud (2012), and Harbash Ibrahim et al. (2015).

5.3. Discussion of the first hypothesis's results

The aforementioned hypothesis posits that teachers of physical education and sports of the Preparatory stage exhibit a moderate level of burnout. and given that the data is a normally distributed, the mean total score of the sample was calculated for the burnout scale, along with its corresponding standard deviation. And a one-sample T-test was subsequently employed, as presented in the following table:

Table 03: Results of the (T) test for one sample to measure the level of burnout

Test Value (0.01)							
Observed t= 2.26							
df (142)							
Dimensions	Mean	Std	Level	Percent	Mean dif	t	Sig
Emotional exhaustion	19.62	10.125	Medium	36.35%			
Depersonalization	3.72	4.55	Low	12.40%	35.531	24.525	0.000
Reduced personal accomplishment	7.11	7.113	Low	14.83%			
Total score of Burnout	30.46	17.324	Low	23.08%			

- The data presented in the table suggests the following details:

The burnout level of the sample is found within the low range, as indicated by the mean (30.46) and the standard deviation (17.32), resulting a rate of 70.21%. Similarly, the parameters of the scale itself are relatively low, except for the dimension of emotional exhaustion, which is only slightly above average. The letter was determined by conducting a one-sample t-test,

which revealed a statistically significant difference between the hypothetical mean and the average mean of burnout at a significance level of 0.01.

This result contradicts what was stated in the hypothesis, except in the dimension of emotional exhaustion, they finding agreed with the study of Hirbash Ibrahim (2015), where it was found that teachers of physical education and sports in Preparatory stage have a low level of burnout, while it differs with the study of Ahmed Ali Al-Harmleh (2007) and QamihaAlaa Mahmoud, (2012), where the level of burnout was medium, as it differed with the study of Esmael Abbas nejad (2013), where the teachers of education had a high level of burnout, and the researcher attributes the reason for this difference to the discrepancy between Samples and measurement tools, on the one hand, and the different circumstances surrounding the teacher, which create a working climate for him that affects him negatively or positively, on the other hand, the average level of emotional exhaustion they have, is considered a justification for the low level of the of dimensions of both depersonalization and the Reduced personal accomplishment, meaning that teachers of physical education and sports in our current study have a good sense of their accomplishments as a result of doing what they can to achieve their goals and accomplish their mission.

5.4. Discussion of the second hypothesis's results

The marital status variable has been found to be a significant factor contributing to differences in burnout levels among teachers of physical education and sports in the preparatory stage, as confirmed by statistical analysis employed by the researcher which is the Mann-Whitney test, as shown in the following table:

Table 04: The "Mann-Whitney" test result for the difference between the sexes in burnout and its dimensions.

Dimensions	marital status	Number	Mean	Std	Sig	Level
Emotional exhaustion	Single	72	19.29	10.111	0.902	Low
	Married	71	19.97	10.199		Low
Depersonalization	Single	72	4.37	4.703	0.046	Low
	Married	71	3.05	4.322		Low
Reduced personal accomplishment	Single	72	7.87	6.862	0.057	Low
	Married	71	6.35	7.327		Low
Total Score	Single	72	31.54	16.961	0.199	Low
	Married	71	29.38	17.739		Low

- The results from table 4 of the test showed that the p-value is greater than the level of significance in the dimension of emotional exhaustion, reduced personal accomplishment, and the overall score of the scale (0.902 -0.057 -0.199), respectively, this indicates the existing of no significant differences in the level of burnout with these dimensions that attributed to the marital status variable. However, the p-value was less than the level of significance in the dimension of depersonalization (0.046), that indicates that there are differences within the same low level in this dimension in favor of single teachers, meaning that the latter suffer from a low level of depersonalization with mean average of (4.37) and a standard deviation of (4.70), while married teachers are at a lower level with an average of (3.05) and a standard deviation of (4.32). The result of the test came against the direction of the hypothesis, and it is a result that is consistent with the study QamihaAlaa Mahmoud (2012) which stated the absence of statistically significant differences in burnout that attributed to the marital status, but it is partially consistent with the study of Ahmed Ali Al Harmleh (2007) in the presence of significant differences in the depersonalization level attributed to the variable of marital status in favor of the single teachers compared to the

married ones. In addition, the results of this study differ with the study of what both Ahmed Ali Al-Harmleh (2007), and Abdulaziz Anwar (2009) which shows a presence of statistically significant differences in burnout level attributed to the marital status in favor of the singer teachers, the researcher attribute the findings to the fact that the state of being married may be a helpful factor in alleviating work pressures by achieving stability for the person, but that is not all the case sense it can also increase it because of responsibilities and the pressures and tasks of life. However, this can differ from one person to another, and the results of this study showed that married teachers generally suffer less from depersonalization than their single peers.

5.5. Discussion of the third hypothesis's results

The hypothesis states that: the teachers of physical education and sports in the preparatory stage have an average level of self-esteem, and because the data does not follow a normal distribution, the researcher used the "Sign Test" to test the hypothesis, with a fixed value of (25), which is a non-parametric test, as shown in the following table:

Table 05: Measuring self-esteem level with Binomial test

Binomial Test							
Self-esteem	Marital Status	Number	Mean	Std	Sig	Level	Percentage
Total Score	25 ≥	6	32.8881	3.911	0.000	Low	93.163 %
	25 <	137					
Total		143					

The results in table 5 indicated that the level of self-esteem among the sample individuals falls within the high level, with a mean average of (32.88), a standard deviation of (3.91), and a percentage of (93.16%). The binomial test shows 137 teachers who obtained 25 degrees, while there are only 6 who have degrees less than or equal to 25 degrees, and since the p-value is less than the significance level (0.05), this means that there is a difference between the average scores of the sample and the hypothetical average value. This result is the opposite of what was stated in the hypothesis, which make it consistent with the study of Harbash Ibrahim (2015), and the study of (Howaida Ismail Ibrahim, 2018), and differs from both Ahmed Ali Al-Haramleh (2007) and Muhannad Abdel Salim (2003) study, that showed an average level for the respondents in its findings.

Another study by Qarumi Abdel-Haq (2014), which resulted in a low level of self-esteem. The researchers believe that the high level of self-esteem among the teachers is evidence of their professional competence and an indication of their ability to perform their duties and assume their responsibilities and their interaction with professional conditions effectively And their compatibility with it, which raises their positive self-esteem and enhances their self-confidence, acceptance and satisfaction, as the value of each person is what he improves, which was improved by Qarumi Abdel-Haq (2014) study, that there is a direct relationship between self-esteem and professional compatibility among teachers of physical education and sports, "studies have also found that individuals who obtain high ranks of excellence and achievement have strict levels of self-evaluation and self-esteem, and on the contrary, lack of self-evaluation and self-esteem may lead the individual to vulnerability in personality and thus the inability to face any difficulty (Muhammad Elas, 2016, p. 168).

5.6. Discussion of the fourth hypothesis's results

This hypothesis stated that: There are statistically significant differences in the self-esteem of teachers of physical education and sports in the preparatory stage attributed to the variable of marital status. The researcher used the Mann-Whitney test to compare the averages of two independent groups that are not normally distributed, and shown as follows:

Table 06: Mann-Whitney test for the difference in self-esteem levels between the two sexes

Self-esteem	Marital status	df	Mean	Std	Sig	Level	Percent
Total Score	Married	72	33.1127	4.12154	0.273	High	82.72%
	Single	71	32.6667	3.70762		High	81.65%

The results of the table showed that there was an increase in the level of self-esteem in favour of married teachers, with a mean average of (33.11), a standard deviation of (4.12), and a percentage of (82.77%), compared to a mean average of (32.66), a standard deviation of (3.70), and a percentage of (81.65%) for single teachers, with a slight difference that is not considered significant, which was confirmed by the p-value result, as it was greater than the level of significance (0.05). This indicates that statistically, there are no significant differences in self-esteem attributed to marital status variable. It is the opposite of what was suggested in the hypothesis and also the opposite of what was found in the MuhannadAbdSalim (2003) study, which statistically showed significant differences in the total score of self-concept in favour of the single teachers; that is, their self-concept is higher than that of married teachers. BelkhirFaiza (2012) study also found an absence of differences in self-concept and its dimensions attributed to the marital status variable.

The researcher justifies this result by pointing out that self-esteem is not exclusive to married couples but is related to a person's view of himself and his satisfaction. There is no doubt that there are several aspects other than marital status, that raise the individual's self-esteem, especially his professional competence, the extent to which he achieves his goals, and his social adjustment, which is something common. All teachers, regardless of whether they are married or unmarried.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the preceding analysis, the present investigation successfully attained its aim and yielded the following findings:

- There is a statistically significant inverse correlation between all dimensions of burnout and its total score, and the level of self-esteem among teachers of physical education and sports in the preparatory stage.
- The marital status variable doesn't indicate any statistically significant differences in the burnout level of teachers, both in terms of the total score level, and in the emotional exhaustion dimension, as well as in the "reduced personal accomplishment" dimension.
- The study reveals a significant statistical difference in the depersonalization dimension between single and married teachers at the same low level. Specifically, the findings indicate that single teachers display a higher level of depersonalization compared to their married counterparts.
- The participants demonstrated a notable degree of self-esteem with a percentage of 93.16%.

- There were no statistically significant differences in self-esteem between married and unmarried teachers. Consequently, we suggest the following actions:
- Developing counseling programs and conducting educational seminars to address the issue of burnout among teachers and emphasize the significance of self-esteem. These initiatives aim to equip teachers with effective coping mechanisms to manage their emotional stress.
- Conducting training programs aimed at enhancing the professional aptitude of teachers and equipping them with requisite competencies for their job is essential given the vital role of this undertaking in improving their self-esteem and alleviating occupational stress.
- Efforts must be made to enhance the professional and social circumstances of teachers in order to elevate their self-esteem.
- Further research could be conducted by incorporating additional demographic variables or exploring their correlation with other psychological phenomena.
- The use of the findings from this study by qualified governing bodies to enhance and advance the educational system.

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